

Energy Inventory in the Sliding and Rolling Regimes

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Abstract:

The energy inventory during the transition between the sliding and rolling regimes has frequently received short shrift in the physics and engineering literature. Here we delve into the intricacies of sliding and rolling motion and emphasize the salient points often missed in a cursory analysis which tends to focus mostly on torque and angular momentum. We show, for instance, that when a spinning cylinder slides and skids and ends up rolling, it loses two-thirds of its initial kinetic energy doing work against friction. Moreover, this number is

independent of the coefficient of friction! This sounds counterintuitive at first blush. We help the reader develop an intuition for these counterintuitive rolling and sliding scenarios by a simple comparison that will remind the reader that they have seen this concept in a more familiar context before. When a car slams on the brakes and skids to a stop the loss of the initial kinetic energy to heat is not dependent on the coefficient of friction. If the coefficient of friction increases the stopping distance decreases and vice versa but the kinetic energy lost to heat remains the same. The more mysterious aspect in the rolling/sliding cylinder is the exact factor $2/3$ regardless of the coefficient of friction. We have programmed an app with App Inventor to simulate various scenarios in order to help develop the intuition which we have found lacking in students of physics and engineering.

Keywords: *sliding, rolling, App Inventor.*

Introduction

The transition between sliding, slipping, and rolling motions is an important topic in engineering and physics. Unfortunately, the various analyses offered in the literature tend to focus on torque and angular momentum. The energy inventory during these regimes receives short shrift. We have provided a detailed analysis of the energy inventory. Moreover, we have programmed an app with App Inventor which clearly depicts visually how the translational and rotational energy components vary as the object transitions to the different regimes. This develops an intuitive sense for the energy stored in the different regimes. Please

contact the author for the App Inventor block code, simulations, and related materials.

Materials and Methods

Consider an object capable of rolling, say a cylinder, ball, or a hoop of mass m and radius r initially spinning clockwise about its major axis with angular velocity ω_i when it is gently dropped on a horizontal surface with coefficient of kinetic friction μ . The frictional force $f = \mu mg$ causes the object to accelerate and since $f = ma$, the linear acceleration of the object is $a = \mu g$. The center of mass velocity of the object after time t will be $v_r = at$ and the horizontal distance traveled by the object is $d = \frac{1}{2} at^2$. The frictional force also generates a torque $\tau = f r$ which slows

down the spinning object. Since $\tau = I \alpha$ where I = moment of inertia and α = angular acceleration, the angular velocity after time t is given by the equation $\omega_f = \omega_i - \alpha t$. The linear velocity keeps increasing and the angular velocity keeps decreasing until the object enters the pure rolling regime. At this point there is no kinetic friction because there is no sliding or slipping or skidding and the equation $v_f = r\omega_f$ is valid.

Let us calculate the time required for pure rolling motion to set in.

From the condition $v_f = r\omega_f$ when pure rolling sets in

$$a t = r (\omega_i - \alpha t)$$

$$\mu g t = r \omega_i - (r \tau / I) t$$

$\mu g t = r \omega_i - f r^2 t / \beta m r^2$ where $\beta = 2/5$ for a solid sphere, $2/3$ for a hollow sphere, $1/2$ for a solid cylinder or disk, and 1 for a hoop.

$$\mu g t = r \omega_i - (f t / m \beta)$$

$$\mu g t = r \omega_i - \mu g t / \beta$$

$$t = [\beta / (\beta+1)] (r \omega_i / \mu g) \quad (1)$$

Since $v_f = at$

$$v_f = \mu g t$$

$$r \omega_f = [\beta / (\beta+1)] r \omega_i$$

$$\omega_f = [\beta / (\beta+1)] \omega_i \quad (2)$$

The numerical values are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1. The Ratios ω_f / ω_i and KE_f / KE_i for a Few Common Objects

Object	β	ω_f / ω_i	KE_f / KE_i
Solid sphere	2/5	2/7	2/7
Hollow Sphere	2/3	2/5	2/5
Solid Cylinder / Disk	1/2	1/3	1/3
Hoop / Ring	1	1/2	1/2

The initial kinetic energy (KE_i) of the spinning object is

$$KE_i = \frac{1}{2} I \omega_i^2$$

$$KE_i = \frac{1}{2} \beta m r^2 \omega_i^2 \quad (3)$$

The final kinetic energy when it enters the pure rolling regime is the sum of the kinetic energy of rotation and the kinetic energy of translation because the center of mass now has a linear component.

$$KE_f = \frac{1}{2} \beta m r^2 \omega_f^2 + \frac{1}{2} m v_f^2$$

We know that $\omega_f = [\beta / (\beta+1)] \omega_i$ and $v_f = r\omega_f$

A couple of steps of algebra gives:

$$KE_f = \frac{1}{2} m r^2 \omega_i^2 \beta^2 / (\beta+1) \quad (4)$$

$$KE_f / KE_i = \beta / (\beta+1) \quad (5)$$

Results

Let us make a couple of observations. When a spinning cylinder slides and skids and ends up rolling, it loses two-thirds of its initial kinetic energy doing work against friction (Fig. 1). Moreover, this number is independent of the coefficient of friction! This sounds counterintuitive at first blush. However, a simple comparison will remind the reader that we have seen this movie in a more familiar context before. When a car slams on the brakes and skids to a stop the loss of the initial kinetic energy to heat is not dependent on the coefficient of friction. If the coefficient of friction increases the stopping distance decreases and vice versa but the kinetic energy lost to heat remains the same. The more mysterious aspect

in the rolling/sliding cylinder is the exact factor $2/3$ regardless of the coefficient of friction. Let us take a closer look at this mysterious number $2/3$ for a cylinder in order to explain its genesis.

How many revolutions does the spinning/skidding cylinder make before pure rolling sets in?

Total number of revolutions = $(1/2\pi) (1/2) (\omega_i + \omega_f) t$

Recall that $t = [\beta / (\beta+1)] (r \omega_i / \mu g)$, $\omega_f = [\beta / (\beta+1)] \omega_i$ and $\beta = 1/2$ for a cylinder.

The total number of revolutions, N , that a cylinder undergoes is given as

$$N = 1/9 r \omega_i^2 / \pi \mu g \quad (6)$$

How many of these revolutions are in the spinning/skidding regime and contribute to the loss of kinetic energy due to work against friction? We must subtract the distance, d , traveled by the center of mass from the total length of contact to get L , which is the effective contact length in the spinning / skidding regime.

The horizontal distance traveled by the center of mass is $d = 1/2 at^2$ and $a = \mu g$ so we get

$$d = 1/18 r^2 \omega_i^2 / \mu g \quad (7)$$

$L = (2\pi r) (\text{Total number of revolutions}) - d$

$$L = (2\pi r) (1/9 r \omega_i^2 / \pi \mu g) - 1/18 r^2 \omega_i^2 / \mu g$$

$$L = 1/6 r^2 \omega_i^2 / \mu g \quad (8)$$

The work done against the frictional force during the spinning/skidding regime is

$$W_f = f L$$

$$W_f = \mu mg L$$

$$W_f = \mu mg (1/6 r^2 \omega_i^2 / \mu g)$$

$$W_f = 1/6 m r^2 \omega_i^2 \quad (9)$$

Taking the energy inventory, we refer to equations (3) and (4) and note that for a cylinder $\beta = 1/2$

$$K.E._i = 1/4 m r^2 \omega_i^2$$

$$K.E._f = 1/12 m r^2 \omega_i^2$$

$$W_f = 1/6 m r^2 \omega_i^2$$

We happily conclude that:

$$K.E._i = K.E._f + W_f$$

Discussion

So far, we have analyzed the energy inventory for the transition from the spinning regime to the pure rolling regime. Now we wish to delve into the energy inventory wherein the object is initially set into sliding motion and ends up in the pure rolling regime. Do we expect the dissipation of the initial kinetic energy caused by work done against friction to be the same? (Fig. 2). In other words, do we expect $KE_f / KE_i = \beta / (\beta+1)$ as depicted in equation (5) to be valid in this case? We will consider a familiar example of a bowling ball that is given an initial sliding velocity v_i .

The frictional force $f = \mu mg$ causes the object to decelerate and since $f = ma$, the linear deceleration of the object is $a = \mu g$. The center of mass velocity of the object after time t will be $v_f = v_i - at$ and the horizontal distance traveled by the object is $d = 1/2 t (v_f + v_i)$. The frictional force also generates a torque $\tau = f r$ which increases the angular velocity of the ball from $\omega_i = 0$ to ω_f when the ball is in the pure rolling regime. Since $\tau = I \alpha$ where the moment of inertia $I = 2/5 m r^2$ we find that the angular acceleration $\alpha = 5/2 \mu g / r$. The angular velocity after time t is given by the equation $\omega_f = \omega_i + \alpha t$. In this case, $\omega_i = 0$. The linear velocity keeps decreasing and the angular velocity keeps increasing until the bowling ball enters the pure rolling regime. Double-click the animated gif depicted in Fig. 1. The App Inventor screenshot is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1. This Figure is Available as an Animated Gif by Emailing the Author: amshakur@salisbury.edu

Figure 2. Smartphone Screenshot of App

At this point there is no kinetic friction because there is no sliding or slipping or skidding and the equation $v_f = r\omega_f$ is valid. We end up with the following two important equations:

$$v_f = v_i - \mu g t \quad (10)$$

$$\omega_f = 5/2 \mu g t / r \quad (11)$$

The time to reach the pure rolling regime and the distance traveled by the center of mass can be determined by imposing the condition $v_f = r\omega_f$ at time t .

From (10) and (11) we obtain:

$$t = 2/7 (v_i / \mu g) \quad (12)$$

$$v_f = 5/7 v_i \quad (13)$$

Since $d = \frac{1}{2} t (v_f + v_i)$, the equation for the distance traveled by the center of mass is:

$$d = 12/49 v_i^2 / \mu g \quad (14)$$

How many revolutions does the bowling ball make before pure rolling sets in?

Total number of revolutions = $(1/2\pi) (1/2) (\omega_i + \omega_f) t$

Recall that $t = 2/7 (v_i / \mu g)$, $\omega_i = 0$, $\omega_f = 5v_i / 7r$ and $t = 2/7 (v_i / \mu g)$

Total number of revolutions, N , that the bowling ball undergoes is given as

$$N = 5 v_i^2 / (98 \pi r \mu g) \quad (15)$$

The effective contact length, L , which contributes to loss of kinetic energy due to friction is

$$L = d - (2\pi r) (N)$$

$$L = 12/49 v_i^2 / \mu g - (2\pi r) (N)$$

$$L = v_i^2 / 7 \mu g$$

The work done against the frictional force before the pure rolling regime is

$$W_f = f L$$

$$W_f = \mu mg L$$

$$W_f = 1/7 m v_i^2 \quad (16)$$

Taking the energy inventory, we note that for the bowling ball with an initial sliding velocity v_i

$$K.E._i = 1/2 m v_i^2 \quad (17)$$

$$K.E._f = 1/2 m v_f^2 + 1/2 I \omega_f^2$$

$$K.E._f = 1/2 m (5/7 v_i)^2 + 1/2 (2/5 m r^2) (5v_i/7r)^2$$

$$K.E._f = 5/14 m v_i^2 \quad (18)$$

From equations (16), (17), and (18), we happily conclude that:

$$K.E._i = K.E._f + W_f$$

As far as energy losses to friction are concerned, does it matter whether an object spins first and then rolls or it slides first and then rolls? (Fig. 3). Let us take a closer look at the bowling ball which was initially given a sliding motion and ended up rolling. We note from equations (17) and (18) that in this case:

$$K.E._f / K.E._i = 5/7$$

Recall that for a bowling ball, $\beta = 2/5$

$$K.E._f / K.E._i = 1/(\beta+1) \quad (19)$$

However, if the bowling ball is set spinning first and then rolls then recall from equation (5) for an object that is set spinning first

$$K.E._f / K.E._i = \beta / (\beta+1) \quad (20)$$

An important conclusion from a comparison of equations (19) and (5) is that an object that is set spinning first loses a lot more kinetic energy to friction than an object that is set sliding first. A

bowling ball that is set sliding first will lose 28.6% of its initial kinetic energy to friction whereas if it is set spinning first it will lose 71.4% of its initial kinetic energy to friction.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have delineated the energy inventory and delved into the intricacies of sliding and rolling motion and emphasized the salient points often missed in a cursory analysis which tends to focus mostly on torque and angular momentum. We have programmed an app with App Inventor 2 to simulate various scenarios in order to help students develop the intuition which we have found lacking in undergraduate students. An important conclusion is that an object that is set spinning first loses a lot more kinetic energy to friction than an object that is set sliding first. A bowling ball that is set sliding first will lose 28.6% of its initial kinetic energy to friction whereas if it is set spinning first it will lose 71.4% of its initial kinetic energy to friction.

References

- Mungan, C.E. (2015). Impulse and work for the bullet-block Veritasium video. *The Physics Teacher*, 53, 325-326. <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.4928342>
- Cross, R. (2015). Rolling to a stop down an inclined plane. *European Journal of Physics*, 36. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0143-0807/36/6/065047>
- Cross, R. (2016). Coulomb's law for rolling friction. *American Journal of Physics*, 84, 221-230. <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.4938149>
- Singh, C. (2002). When physics intuition fails. *American Journal of Physics*, 70, 1103-1109. <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.1512659>
- Shakur, A. (2015). Bullet-Block Science Video Puzzle. *The Physics Teacher*, 53, 15-16. <https://doi.org/10.1119/1.4904234>